

DEGRADATION MAPS DEVELOPED WITH THE HELP OF GEOINFORMATION SYSTEM TECHNOLOGIES OF BUKHARA DISTRICT OF BUKHARA REGION**Karshiboev Kh.***PhD student**Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemical Research***Bobomurodov Sh.***Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemical Research,**DSc***Bakhodirov Z.***Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemical Research**PhD*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13908172>**Abstract**

Detailed digital soil maps were created using ArcGIS software to analyze the soil properties of agricultural areas in the Bukhara district, Bukhara region. These maps provided insights into the mechanical composition of the soil, levels of organic matter (humus), nutrient availability, and salinity parameters based on the geographical information systems technologies.

Keywords: GIS technologies, soil degradation, regional analysis; soil parameters, humus, soil salinity, nutrient elements, digital maps.

Introduction. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 33% of the world's soils have been degraded, and this degradation may continue to reach 90% by 2050 [1].

In our republic, the quality and composition of the irrigated soils are changing every year. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the degradation processes affecting soil fertility and develop scientific solutions to prevent these negative processes, as well as to increase and protect soil fertility. Relevant measures are being implemented, including the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5742 "On measures for effective use of land and water resources in agriculture" and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 10, 2022 "On effective Picht against land degradation" (Resolution No. PQ-277). These decrees focus on creating a system to prevent and combat land degradation, desertification, and drought, as well as restoring degraded lands and widely introducing advanced technologies in this direction [2].

To support these efforts, activities are being carried out, such as monitoring agricultural lands, using geodetic data and cartographic materials, conducting

aerospace, topographic-geodetic, cartographic, soil, and geobotanical research, creating cartographic works using remote sensing data, and organizing the widespread use of modern information and communication technologies [3].

Given the importance of these issues, there is a need to study the processes of agricultural land degradation based on geoinformation technologies and cartographic methods.

The research object is Bukhara district which is geographically located in the southeastern part of Bukhara region, bordering Kogon district in the north, Qarovulbazar district in the east, Olot district in the south, and Jondor district in the west. The land area of the district is 84,962 hectares, total agricultural land is 53,265 hectares, of which 22,612 hectares are irrigated cropland.

Research methods. In the assessment of degradation in agricultural areas of Bukhara district, Bukhara region, complex studies were carried out on the main soil indicators, the availability of humus, nutrient elements, salinity levels of the soil in the area, data on their spatial distribution based on (1:10000 scale) thematic maps were developed.

Pic-1.

Field-research works were completed, and soil samples were taken from the soil sections marked on the field map in the order determined by genetic layers, and Field and laboratory research work was carried out according to the methods developed and generally accepted at Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemical Research. Data obtained from research results are entered into the ArcGIS program and thematic maps are drawn [6]. For this, the interpolation methods available in the Geostatistical Analyst (GA) module of the ArcGIS program were used [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Compilation of electronic digital maps of irrigated meadow, meadow-alluvial, meadow-swamp, sandy-desert soils in the massifs of Bukhara district consists of the following actions:

1. Preparatory works;

2. Compilation of the thematic layers of the map and corresponding tables, their analysis. Creating a database;

3. Entering table with classification of objects (attributes) and text data;

4. Development of a system of legends;

5. Placing thematic layers of the map, creating a cartographic image and editing them;

6. Development of the composition of the map and its preparation for publication;

7. Map publication [7].

By performing these actions, using the ArcGIS program, it is necessary to know its scale, how many areas are reflected in it, which elements are primary and which are secondary, which materials are used to show the processes, the characteristics of the area, etc [8].

All information about the area should be included in this database (Pic-2)

Pic-2 Database is created in the ArcCatalog section of ArcGIS

After the database is created, digital maps are created in the ArcMap section of ArcGIS (Pic. 3).

Pic-3. Digital mapping works in the ArcMap

Using the ArcGIS program, conditional symbols are created sequentially on electronic digital maps. Based on the method of creating maps of the research area and the selected cartographic method, the legend of the map can be made semi-automatically [9].

Key soil indicators were mapped using ESRI's ArcGIS software and 1:10,000 scale was added to each soil indicator map and separated.

The places where soil samples were taken in the region are identified and general information is entered. The map was colored and changed depending on the input data (amount of humus, availability of mobile phosphorus and exchangeable potassium in the soil, salinity level).

According to the results of the analysis, in the evaluation of the degradation of meadow, meadow alluvial, meadow-swamp, sandy-desert soils in the irrigated land areas of Bukhara district of Bukhara region,

these were evaluated according to these main soil indicators:

1. Mechanical composition of soil

According to the mechanical composition of the irrigated meadow, meadow alluvial, meadow-swamp, sandy-desert soils of the Bukhara oasis, 162.6 ha is clay, 3360.3 ha is heavy loamy, 13716.5 is medium loamy, 2658.5 ha is light loamy, 858.4 ha is sandy loam and 470.9 ha is sandy mechanical composition.

According to the results of the analysis, 20.10% of the area of the studied area is considered to be light loamy and sandy lands, which are prone to degradation according to their mechanical composition and are classified as difficult to develop.

2. Dehumification

More than 40 percent of the irrigated land in our republic is supplied with humus at a low and very low

level. As a result of the rapid decomposition (mineralization) of the organic matter (humus) in the soil of the irrigated areas of the district, mineral compounds that cannot be fed to plants are formed. As a result, the composition and structure of the soil and its agronomic indicators (moistening, water permeability, heat retention

and similar physical, chemical and biological properties and characteristics) were negatively changed. It was found that the soils distributed in all massifs of Bukhara district are provided with humus at a very low (up to 1%, 18969.1 hectares) and low (1.1-2.0%, 1739.8 hectares) level (Pic. 4).

Pic-4. Humus supply map of irrigated lands of Bukhara district, Bukhara region

According to the analysis, 85.04% of the scattered soils in the district had up to 1% humus content, while 14.96% had 1.1-2% humus. These results indicate a strong dehumification process, leading to severe soil degradation in the area.

3. Nutrient Depletion:

The composition of nutrients in the soil is a critical factor regulating the productivity and quality of agricultural crops. The growth and development of plants are deeply affected by the availability of essential nutrients, such as phosphorus and potassium, in the soil.

However, the levels of these nutrients in the soils of the republic have been decreasing over the years.

Over the years, the areas with "very low" phosphorus supply have increased by 170,600 hectares, while the "poorly" supplied areas have increased by 149,400 hectares. Conversely, the areas with "high" phosphorus supply have increased by only 26,000 hectares, and the "very high" supply areas have decreased by 97,000 hectares.

Pic-5. Map of availability of mobile phosphorus of irrigated lands of Bukhara region, Bukhara district

Similarly, the areas with "very low" potassium availability in the soil have increased to 140,000 hectares, the "low" availability areas have increased to 215,000 hectares, and the "average" availability areas have increased to 89,000 hectares. Meanwhile, the areas with "high" and "very high" potassium levels have decreased by 63,300 hectares.

According to the level of availability of mobile phosphorus, the soils of the studied area fell into the categories of very low and low availability, and their area was 19487 hectares or 83.57% of the total area. In general, the soils distributed in the district are mobile phosphorus and exchange provided with potassium much less than the average amounts, and it was noted that the soils of these regions are in degradation according to the nutrient depletion indicator (Pic. 5).

In the irrigated lands of the Bukhara oasis, potassium is mostly found in the soil in the form of minerals such as orthoclase, muscovite, biotite, and nepheline.

However, these forms of potassium are not readily available for plant absorption or are difficult for plants to assimilate.

Despite the soils in the research area being rich in potassium, the amount of mobile, plant-available forms of potassium has been decreasing in the irrigated soils in recent years. The main reason for this is the low application of potassium fertilizers in recent years.

An assessment of the exchangeable potassium levels revealed that 107.6 hectares are very low (0-100 mg/kg), 1797.4 hectares are low (101-200 mg/kg), and only 14.2 hectares are moderately supplied. In total, 88.2% of the area has very low to low exchangeable potassium levels (Pic. 6).

Similarly, the soils distributed in the district are much less supplied with mobile phosphorus and exchangeable potassium compared to average amounts, indicating nutrient depletion and degradation of the soils in these regions. (Pic. 6).

Pic-6. Map of exchangeable potassium of irrigated lands of Bukhara district of Bukhara region

Regarding soil salinity, the negative effects of excess salts in the irrigated soils of Bukhara district are as follows: it directly affects the soil structure, causing compaction and reduced water infiltration, poor air exchange, and inducing osmotic stress in plants, leading to dehydration and reduced water uptake. Excess toxic salts can also disrupt the balance of key ions like calcium and magnesium, leading to the formation of toxic compounds or nutrient deficiencies for plants.

According to the water absorption analysis, the soils in the region are saline to varying degrees: 46.9% are non-saline, 32.3% are weakly saline, 16.3% are moderately saline, and 4.3% are strongly saline, compared to the total agricultural land area of 2045.3 thousand hectares (Pic. 7).

Pic-7. Soil salinity map of irrigated lands of Bukhara district of Bukhara region

According to the field research conducted in the irrigated soils of Bukhara district and the chemical analysis of soil samples, the soils in the region exhibit varying degrees of salinity - weak, moderate, and strong.

As evident from the data, the soils in the district are heavily influenced by salinization, and soil salinity is a widespread issue in these areas.

In conclusion, The information on soil health indicators is crucial for mapping the degradation processes. Accurate and reliable data is necessary to guide crop selection, monitor changes in adverse conditions, and effectively implement restoration or protection strategies for the land. Based on the analytical data obtained, the thematic maps of soil indicators developed using GIS technologies can play a vital role in assessing the state of degradation in the agricultural land areas of Bukhara district. These maps are particularly important

for monitoring the degradation processes occurring in the irrigated meadows, alluvial, and sandy-desert soils, evaluating the risk of degradation, and developing measures to improve and protect the condition of soils used for agriculture.

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